

Review

Theoretical Overview on the Use of Sustainable Building Materials in Modern Era

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Abstract: By analyzing the environmental, energy-saving, and durability performance of sustainable building materials, it is found that they have advantages in carbon emissions, resource conservation, insulation, light utilization, service life, and adaptability. Studied the advantages and application of sustainable building materials, analyzed the reasons for their application in modern architectural design, and proposed measures and strategies to promote their use. Analyzing bamboo and wood, ecological roofs, and solar photovoltaic panels as typical application cases, proposing strategies to promote the application of sustainable building materials: policy support, technological innovation, and educational promotion are important measures, including formulating environmental protection policies, providing financial support, promoting research and development, and conducting education and training; Strengthen policy guidance, improve material performance and quality, enhance education and publicity, and improve public awareness and understanding. By implementing these effective measures, the use of sustainable building materials will be pushed to new heights.

Keywords: Sustainable building materials; Modern architectural design; Policy support; technological innovation Design standards; Education and publicity

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1. Introduction

1.1 Environmental performance

Sustainable building materials typically use environmentally friendly and renewable materials such as bamboo, wood, and wood fibers. The production, processing, and use of these materials can reduce pollution and damage to the environment. Compared with traditional building materials, sustainable building materials can reduce carbon emissions, reduce the burning of grass, trees, and straw, and have a positive effect on mitigating global climate change. Traditional building materials use materials such as gypsum and cement, which consume a lot of energy and raw materials in the production process. The environmentally friendly and renewable materials used in sustainable building materials, such as biomass materials and materials for recycling and reusing waste materials, can effectively save resources. The use of these environmentally friendly materials on the exterior of the building can create a textured

facade that is realistic and realistic; Simplified regional elements are used in some parts of the building, and the cultural characteristics of the building can be reflected through local environmentally friendly materials and regional elements.

1.2 Energy saving performance

Sustainable building materials typically have good thermal insulation properties, which can effectively reduce the energy consumption of buildings. For example, buildings that use efficient insulation materials can maintain coolness in summer and warmth in winter, thereby reducing the use of air conditioning and heating systems. Under the requirements of energy-saving design for green buildings, the use of new decorative insulation integrated board materials can reduce construction difficulty, minimize construction frequency, improve construction efficiency, and ensure the flatness of exterior decorative walls.

Sustainable building materials also focus on fully utilizing natural light in design and selection, reducing dependence on artificial light sources, and achieving energy-saving goals. For example, by selecting building materials with high transparency, underground buildings adopt a light guide tube type sunlight introduction system, and use new materials and technologies to reduce electricity consumption; The fiber optic sunlight introduction system can help renovate existing buildings to meet lighting design requirements, reduce the implementation difficulty of renovation projects, meet user requirements, and improve comfort.

1.3 Durability Performance

Sustainable building materials typically have a long service life and strong durability, which can reduce the frequency of building maintenance and replacement, thereby reducing environmental pollution. For example, using new waterproof materials with longer service life and stronger durability can reduce the number of roof and exterior wall waterproof repairs during later use.

Sustainable building materials typically have strong adaptability and can cope with changes in various environmental and climatic conditions. For example, adopting an ecological roof can reduce the temperature and energy consumption of buildings, while also preventing rainwater retention and leakage, improving the durability and comfort of buildings.

2. Application of sustainable building materials

2.1 Current Status of Sustainable Building Materials Application in China

With the increasing emphasis on environmental protection and sustainable development, the domestic market for sustainable building materials is gradually growing and expanding. At present, sustainable building materials are used in the fields of new construction, renovation, and maintenance of old buildings. In addition, the government is continuously increasing its support for sustainable building materials, encouraging enterprises to research and promote sustainable building materials.

At present, the application scope of sustainable building materials in China is very extensive, including wall materials, roof materials, floor materials, insulation materials, thermal insulation materials, waterproof materials, etc. For example, new lightweight wall materials, which can utilize garbage and slag, can reduce waste emissions. At the same time, the insulation and crack resistance of new materials are better than traditional energy consuming materials. Recyclable reinforced concrete, ecological building materials, etc. have been widely used and play an irreplaceable role.

2.2 Current Status of Sustainable Building Materials Application Abroad

In foreign countries, the application of sustainable building materials has become extremely popular and has become mainstream in the construction industry. In developed countries such as Europe and the Americas, governments, businesses, and the public attach immense importance to the application and promotion of sustainable building materials and have formulated corresponding policies and standards to strongly support the development and application of sustainable building materials, achieving sustainable development of the ecological environment.

The application scope of sustainable building materials abroad is very wide, including new steel, environmentally friendly wood, biomass materials, green concrete, etc. These materials have high environmental performance, durability, and energy-saving performance, and have been widely used and recognized.

2.3 Typical Cases of Sustainable Building Materials Application

Bamboo and wood are environmentally friendly and renewable materials with excellent properties such as lightweight, high strength, thermal insulation, and sound insulation. In recent years, many buildings at home and abroad have used bamboo wood, such as Shanghai center Tower, Singapore Haojiang Tower, and so on. Their excellent architectural effects and environmental performance have been widely recognized.

Ecological roof is a new type of sustainable building material that can utilize natural vegetation and soil to effectively absorb and purify rainwater, improve the insulation, and sound insulation performance of buildings, reduce the use of insulation materials for roof construction, and beautify the urban environment. More buildings both domestically and internationally are adopting eco-friendly roofs, such as the Berlin City Hall in Germany and the Shanghai World Financial Center.

Solar photovoltaic panels are a renewable energy source with excellent properties such as green, environmentally friendly, efficient, and stable. The use of solar photovoltaic panels can convert solar energy into electrical energy, providing clean energy for buildings. China is one of the world's largest countries in the photovoltaic industry, and photovoltaic power generation, as a sustainable energy source, is increasingly valued in modern architectural design. Taking Beijing Daxing International Airport as an example, the airport covers a large area of photovoltaic panels on the roof of the terminal building, achieving an organic combination of building and photovoltaic power generation. This design not only meets the energy-saving and environmental protection requirements of buildings, but also provides reliable clean energy for airports, contributing to the realization of green development.

3. Reasons for using sustainable building materials in modern architectural design

3.1 National policy support

The global environmental problems are becoming increasingly serious, and countries have begun to introduce a series of environmental policies to promote the coordination between economic development and sustainable development. China started late in the research of sustainable utilization of building materials but has also achieved internationally recognized results.

With the continuous increase of global greenhouse gas emissions, climate change is becoming increasingly severe. To address climate change, countries have put forward goals such as carbon peaking and carbon neutrality. Among them, carbon peaking refers to reaching the peak of greenhouse gas emissions as early as possible, while carbon neutrality refers to reducing net carbon emissions to zero. To achieve these goals, governments and organizations around the world have begun to take measures, one of which is to reduce the environmental impact of the construction industry by promoting the use of sustainable building materials.

The support of national policies is one of the crucial factors in promoting the application of sustainable building materials. At present, the government's policy measures for sustainable building materials include financial support, tax reductions, and policy guidance. For example, the Ministry of Finance has issued a notice on encouraging green building demonstration projects, encouraging enterprises to research and apply sustainable building materials to promote the sustainable development of the construction industry.

3.2 Sustainable Development Requirements for the Construction Industry

As a vital component of the national economy, the construction industry has a significant impact on energy consumption and the environment, and also has an important responsibility to promote sustainable development.

In the current environment of environmental protection and sustainable development, the construction industry needs to transform and upgrade, promote green, environmentally friendly, and sustainable building design and construction, and promote the application and development of sustainable building materials. This can not only reduce the energy consumption and pollution of buildings, minimize environmental damage, but also improve the quality and value of buildings, meeting people's needs for healthy, comfortable, and safe living.

3.3 Market demand for sustainable building materials

With the progress of society and the improvement of people's environmental awareness, the demand for sustainable building materials in the market is also increasing day by day.

Sustainable building materials have excellent properties such as environmental protection, energy efficiency, and durability, and are an indispensable part of modern architectural design. Driven by market demand, more buildings are adopting sustainable building materials, such as new steel, ecological building materials, solar photovoltaic panels, light guide tube type sunlight introduction systems, new waterproof materials, new decorative insulation integrated panels, etc. Their applications have been widely recognized and promoted. Meanwhile, with the continuous innovation and development of sustainable building materials technology, the market demand for more environmentally friendly, energy-efficient, and durable building materials is also increasing.

4. Countermeasures and measures to promote the application of sustainable building materials

4.1 Policy Support

The application of sustainable building materials requires the government to introduce a series of environmental policies, encourage enterprises to develop and apply sustainable building materials, and increase the market share of sustainable building materials. Specific measures include:

Establish an environmental policy framework. The government should establish an environmental policy framework, formulate relevant policies for sustainable building materials, strengthen environmental supervision and guidance, guide enterprises to adopt sustainable building materials, and ensure the market demand for sustainable building materials.

Intensify efforts in environmental protection policies. The government can increase the intensity of environmental protection policies, strengthen the supervision of building materials that do not meet environmental requirements, increase the illegal costs of non-compliant enterprises, and promote the application and marketization of sustainable building materials.

Encourage the use of sustainable building materials. The government can provide tax exemptions or subsidies to enterprises that use sustainable building materials that meet environmental requirements, encourage them to adopt sustainable building materials, and promote the application and development of sustainable building materials.

The government can provide financial support to enterprises, encourage them to invest in research and development and production of sustainable building materials, and enhance the market competitiveness of sustainable building materials. Specific measures include:

Reduce or waive taxes. The government can provide tax incentives for sustainable building materials enterprises, improve their production cost-effectiveness, and reduce the market price of sustainable building materials.

Financial support. The government can provide financial support to sustainable building materials enterprises, support their production and research and development, and promote the promotion and application of sustainable building materials.

Establish a fund. The government can establish funds to support the research and production of sustainable building materials, attract more enterprises to join the field of sustainable building materials, and promote the marketization of sustainable building materials.

The government can establish a record of green building material standards, guide the construction industry to recognize sustainable building materials, and promote the development and application of sustainable buildings.

Develop green building standards. The government can establish green building standards, clarify the scope and standards of sustainable building materials, guide building design and construction units to adopt sustainable building material design basis, and improve the application rate of sustainable building materials.

Raise the requirements for green building standards. The government can gradually increase the requirements for green building standards, encourage enterprises to develop and apply more environmentally friendly and sustainable

building materials, increase opportunities for the use of sustainable building materials, and gradually phase out energy consuming materials that cannot meet design standards.

Encourage green building certification. The government can encourage enterprises to obtain green building certification, encourage construction companies to use sustainable building materials that meet green building standards, and increase the market share of green building materials.

4.2 Technological Innovation

Enterprises can increase research and development investment, continuously innovate production processes and application technologies for sustainable building materials and improve the performance and quality of sustainable building materials.

Enterprises can introduce modern technologies such as digital design and 3D printing to improve production efficiency and product quality, reduce costs, and promote the application and promotion of sustainable building materials.

Enterprises can strengthen technological cooperation and collaborate with other enterprises, universities, and research institutions to accelerate the progress and promotion of sustainable building materials technology.

4.3 Countermeasure research

The government should formulate sustainable building materials policies, clarify the support and guidance measures for the application of sustainable building materials, and provide policy guarantees for the application of sustainable building materials.

Promotion and advertising. The government should enhance public awareness and understanding of sustainable building materials through publicity and promotion and encourage enterprises to develop and apply sustainable building materials.

Financial support. The government can introduce funding support policies to encourage enterprises to develop and produce sustainable building materials and promote the marketization of sustainable building materials.

Policy guidance. The government can encourage enterprises to develop and apply sustainable building materials through tax incentives, subsidies, and exemptions, and promote the marketization of sustainable building materials.

The government can strengthen financial support, introduce funding support policies, guide enterprises to research and produce sustainable building materials, and promote the marketization of sustainable building materials.

Provide low interest loans. The government can provide low interest loans to enterprises, encourage them to invest in research and development and production of sustainable building materials, and reduce their capital costs.

Financial subsidies. The government can provide funding subsidies to enterprises to encourage them to invest in research and development and production of sustainable building materials, thereby enhancing the market competitiveness of sustainable building materials.

5. Conclusion

With the increasing emphasis on environmental protection and sustainable development, the use of sustainable building materials in modern architectural design has become an inevitable trend and key factor in the development of green building materials today. Against the backdrop of the global wave of carbon neutrality and energy scarcity, global sustainable development is of great significance for promoting energy conservation and emission reduction and building green homes. It will also become a direction that governments and enterprises around the world will strive to advocate and achieve in the future.

The government plays a crucial role in promoting sustainable building materials. The government can formulate corresponding policies, provide more policy support and incentive measures, and encourage enterprises to research and promote sustainable building materials. For example, the government can increase support for sustainable building material production enterprises and encourage them to increase their promotion efforts. In addition, the government can reduce the price of sustainable building materials through financial subsidies and other means, establish design

standards for new materials, increase government registration for new materials, to increase market demand and promote the application of sustainable building materials.

In terms of technological innovation, the construction industry can strengthen research and development of sustainable building materials to improve their performance and quality. For example, developing more environmentally friendly and durable building materials can reduce environmental pollution and the generation of construction waste. In addition, more energy-efficient and environmentally friendly building technologies can also be developed, such as utilizing clean energy sources such as solar and wind power to improve the energy-saving performance of buildings. Public education is also an important way to promote sustainable building materials. We should strengthen public response to knowledge education, enhance technological innovation, establish new concepts, develop new theories, and stimulate new products.

In summary, the government, construction industry, and the public should actively participate in the promotion of sustainable building materials. Only through joint efforts from all parties can we better promote the application of sustainable building materials and achieve the goals of environmental protection, energy conservation, and sustainable building development.

References

- Alqahtani FK, Ghataora G, Khan MI, et al. Lightweight concrete containing recycled plastic aggregates. 2015 international conference on electromechanical control technology and transportation, Montréal, QC, Canada, 12–15 May 2015. .
- Bheel N, Ali MOA, Khahro SH, et al. Experimental study on fresh, mechanical properties and embodied carbon of concrete blended with sugarcane bagasse ash, metakaolin, and millet husk ash as ternary cementitious material. *Environ Sci Pollut Control Ser* 2022; 29(4): 5224–5239.
- Brzyski P, Widomski M. The influence of partial replacement of hemp shives by expanded perlite on physical properties of hemp-lime composite. *AIP Conf Proc* 2017; 1866(1). .
- Chakraborty D, Elzarka H. Advanced machine learning techniques for building performance simulation: a comparative analysis. *Journal of Building Performance Simulation* 2019; 12(2): 193–207. .
- Chakraborty D, Elzarka H. Advanced machine learning techniques for building performance simulation: a comparative analysis. *Journal of Building Performance Simulation* 2019; 12(2): 193–207. .
- Charai M, Mghazli MO, Channouf S, et al. Lightweight waste-based gypsum composites for building temperature and moisture control using coal fly ash and plant fibers. *Construct Build Mater* 2023; 393. . .
- Corinaldesi V, Moriconi G. Use of synthetic fibers in self-compacting lightweight aggregate concretes. *J Build Eng* 2015; 4: 247–254. .
- de Brito J, Robles R. Recycled aggregate concrete (RAC) methodology for estimating its long-term properties. *Indian J Eng Mater Sci* 2010; 17(6): 449–462. .
- Emad MZ, Mitri HS, Henning JG. Effect of blast vibrations on the stability of cemented rockfill. *Int J Min Reclamat Environ* 2012; 26: 233–243. .
- Endo N, Shimoda E, Goshome K, et al. Simulation of design and operation of hydrogen energy utilization system for a zero emission building. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2019; 44(14): 7118–7124. .
- Farrukh B, Younis I, Longsheng C. The impact of natural resource management, innovation, and tourism development on environmental sustainability in low-income countries. *Resour Pol* 2023; 86. .
- Feng SJ, Li J, Zheng QT, et al. Utilization potential of waste residue and dust powder from C&D waste. *Case Stud Constr Mater* 2023; 19: e02513. .

- Jayasinghe G, Tokashiki Y, Kitou M. Development of synthetic lightweight soil aggregates utilizing coal fly ash and mine clay as waste materials. *Tropical Agricultural Research Extension* 2005; 8. https://www.agri.ruh.ac.lk/tare/pdf/V_8/AG.8.1.pdf
- Kymäläinen HR, Sjöberg AM. Flax and hemp fibres as raw materials for thermal insulations. *Build Environ* 2008; 43(7): 1261–1269. . ISI.
- Pearlmutter D, Theochari D, Nehls T, et al. Enhancing the circular economy with nature-based solutions in the built urban environment: green building materials, systems and sites. *Blue-Green Systems* 2020; 2(1): 46–72. .
- Ruggerio CA. Sustainability and sustainable development: a review of principles and definitions. *Sci Total Environ* 2021; 786. .
- Rukhaiyar S, Samadhiya NK. Strength behaviour of sandstone subjected to polyaxial state of stress. *Int J Min Sci Technol* 2017; 27(6): 889–897. .
- Sai Trivedi S, Snehal K, Das BB, et al. A comprehensive review towards sustainable approaches on the processing and treatment of construction and demolition waste. *Construct Build Mater* 2023; 393. .
- Shaheen N, Khushnood RA, Memon SA, et al. Feasibility assessment of newly isolated calcifying bacterial strains in self-healing concrete. *Construct Build Mater* 2023; 362. .
- Teotónio I, Cabral M, Cruz CO, et al. Decision support system for green roofs investments in residential buildings. *J Clean Prod* 2020; 249. .
- Vázquez-López A, Ao X, del Río Saez JS, et al. Triboelectric nanogenerator (TENG) enhanced air filtering and face masks: recent advances. *Nano Energy* 2023; 108635. .
- Walker R, Pavía S. Moisture transfer and thermal properties of hemp-lime concretes. *Construct Build Mater* 2014; 64: 270–276. .
- Xie X, Gou Z. Building performance simulation as an early intervention or late verification in architectural design: same performance outcome but different design solutions. *Journal of Green Building* 2017; 12(1): 45–61. .
- Ye X, Rasoulinezhad E. Assessment of impacts of green bonds on renewable energy utilization efficiency. *Renew Energy* 2023; 202: 626–633. .
- Zhou X, Li H, Lu C. An environment-friendly thermal insulation material from cotton stalk fibers. *Energy Build* 2010; 42(7): 1070–1074.

